

Design And Fabrication of Self Balancing Two-Wheeler Vehicle Using Gyroscope

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Abstract:

As a sustainable mode of transportation in urban settings, electric two-wheelers are gaining popularity. For these vehicles to operate safely and effectively, achieving ideal balance and stability is crucial. The goal of this project is to better understand how weight distribution and gyroscopic characteristics can improve the balance and stability of electric two-wheeler without revealing any specific graphical information. A pivotal factor in an electric two-wheeler's equilibrium is its weight distribution. This study aims to identify the ideal weight distribution between the front and rearwheels to reduce the risk of tipping over during dynamic maneuvers through meticulous analysis and experimentation. We hope to achieve a more balanced and secure ride by carefully redistributing the weight, particularly during turns and abrupt stop. Additionally, the implementation of gyroscopic components in electric two-wheeler will be investigated. The rotating wheels' gyroscopic forces significantly increase stability. In order to further enhance the vehicle's overall balance and control, this project will look into ways to enhance these gyroscopic effects, perhaps through the use of cutting-edge materials or wheel designs. By harnessing gyroscopic forces and optimizing weight distribution without relying on graphical data, this research project aims to advance the state-of-the-art in electric two-wheeler design. The findings of this research could result in safer and more reliable electric two-wheeler, encouraging their adoption as a green and effective mode of urban transportation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Two-wheeled vehicles with parallel spin axis wheels come in several varieties. Usually, they are utilized for leisure or transportation. Lighter vehicles with smaller engines are usually cheaper than their heavier counterparts and is the primary means of transport in a lot of Asian countries. Nowadays maximum road accidents are of the two wheelers. Needless to say, a lot of investment goes into manufacturing and development of state-of the-art high technology motor bikes but none can guarantee road safety and it solely depends upon the rider and hence road accidents occur as the person riding the bike loses control over it and the bike falls. Also, while learning to ride bicycles children are often afraid to ride as there is a fear of falling. To avoid such tragic scenarios, a mechanical gyroscope can be installed in the vehicles. It utilizes electromechanical components and operates on the inverted pendulum concept, providing one person with a method of transportation. Naturally unstable, the two-wheeled self-balancing vehicle is a non-linear multivariable. Since

controlling such a system is difficult, study has focused on it. If the user tilts forward, it will move forward; if they tilt backward, it will move backward. The vehicle described in this paper has all of its mechanical and electrical parts created from the ground up, manufactured, connected, and tested. This car can be seen as an environmentally friendly, battery-operated, and very user-friendly system.

2. GYROSCOPE

2.1 Working Principle

Gravity is the foundation for a gyroscope's operation. The gyroscopic precession in the spinning wheel is explained as the result of the product of angular momentum, which is felt by the torque on a disc. The tendency of a rotating item to maintain its orientation is known as gyroscopic motion or gyroscopic force. We know that the rotating object possesses angular momentum, which needs to be conserved. This is done because when there is any change in the axis of rotation, there will be a change in the orientation, which changes the angular momentum. As a result, it is possible to conclude that the gyroscope's operating principle is based on angular momentum conservation.

2.2 Laws of Gyroscope

1) First Law of Gyroscope: If a rotating wheel is so maintained as to be free to move about any axis passing through its center of mass, its spin axis will remain fixed in space.

2) Second Law of Gyroscope: A spinning mass will rotate at an angular velocity about an axis perpendicular to both of the aforementioned axes when a torque operates on its axis of spin, $\Omega = T/I\omega$.

3. OBJECTIVES & APPLICATIONS OF GYROSCOPE

3.1 Objectives

- **Stability:** Gyroscopes help maintain stability by detecting shifts in balance and adjusting the vehicle's orientation accordingly. This stability feature makes them easier to ride, even for beginners.
- **Safety:** By stabilizing the vehicle, gyroscopes contribute to enhanced safety. They help prevent sudden falls or accidents caused by loss of balance, reducing the risk of injury for riders.
- **Maneuverability:** While maintaining stability, self-balancing electric vehicles with gyroscopes remain highly maneuverable. They can navigate through tight spaces and handle corners smoothly, offering a convenient mode of transportation in urban environments.
- **Efficiency:** Gyroscopic stabilization allows for efficient energy usage, as the vehicle adjusts its balance without requiring excessive power input from the rider. This can contribute to longer battery life and extended travel distances.
- **User-Friendly:** The self-balancing feature simplifies the riding experience, making it accessible to a wide range of users regardless of their prior experience with similar vehicles. This user-friendly design encourages adoption and promotes sustainable transportation alternatives.
- **Adaptability:** Gyroscopic technology can adapt to various terrains and riding conditions, ensuring consistent stability and performance whether on flat surfaces, inclines, or uneven terrain.
- **Enhanced Control:** Riders can enjoy greater control over the vehicle's movements due to the precise adjustments facilitated by gyroscopes. This control leads to a smoother and more comfortable riding experience.
- **Innovation:** Incorporating gyroscopic stabilization into electric vehicles demonstrates technological innovation, attracting consumers interested in cutting-edge transportation solutions.

3.2 Application of Gyroscope

- **Automotive Safety Systems:** Gyroscopes are employed in electronic stability control (ESC) systems in automobiles to improve vehicle stability and prevent skidding or loss of control during cornering or sudden maneuvers. They also play a role in rollover detection and deployment of airbags in the event of a crash.
- **Consumer Electronics:** Gyroscopes are commonly found in smartphones, tablets, and wearable devices to enable features like screen rotation, gesture recognition, and activity tracking. They contribute to the user experience by enhancing device functionality and responsiveness.
- **Robotics:** Gyroscopes are utilized in robotics for balance control, motion planning, and obstacle avoidance. They help robots maintain stability while moving on uneven terrain or performing tasks that require precise coordination and orientation.
- **Aerospace and Defense:** Gyroscopes are used in aerospace applications such as attitude control systems for satellites, missile guidance systems, and aircraft autopilots. They provide critical feedback for maintaining desired orientations and trajectories in space or combat scenarios.
- **Industrial Equipment:** Gyroscopes are incorporated into industrial machinery and equipment for monitoring rotational speed, detecting vibrations, and ensuring smooth operation. They help optimize performance, reduce downtime, and prevent equipment failures.

4. LITERATUREREVIEW

J. P. Meijaard, Jim M. Papadopoulos, Andy Ruina, A. L. Schwab (2011): In their work, they used a gyroscope to construct a self-balancing two-wheeler. The rotation of the mild steel disc mounted on the motor shaft produces the gyroscopic effect.

Published in: International Journal of Engineering and Technology

Pallavi Gogoi, Manish Nath, Bumi Trueman Doley, Abhijit Boruah (2017): In their work they used mild disc mounted on a motor shaft which produces gyroscope effects to self-balance vehicle.

Published in: "International Journal of Engineering & Technology".

5. CONSTRUCTION & WORKING MECHANISM

5.1 Construction

Drilling and CNC lathe operations are used in the manufacturing of the gyroscope disk. The bottom steel base of the steel frame is attached to it. The bottom steel base is equipped with round-edge wheels, and the frame is pierced with holes to accommodate the gyroscope assembly's gimble. A U-bracketed DC motor is positioned above the gimble. The mass distribution must be predominately on the upper side of the gimble (top heavy arrangement) in order for this design to function. Thus, the centre of gravity is slightly above the gimble axis. The motor shaft is connected with a mild steel disk that serves as a gyroscope. The DC motor's shaft is fastened to a steel hub that has holes punched in its top flat surface for the purpose of eventually fastening the gyroscope disc by attaching it to the hub. The DC motor is bolted to the U-bracket, which allows it to remain intact with it. Mild steel was utilized to create the gyroscope disc, hub, steel frame, and U-bracket. Ultimately, different sized bolts and nuts were utilized to put the complete model together. A crucial design decision we made for this model was to allow the gyroscope disc to hang freely inside the U-bracket that is attached to the steel frame. In order to achieve free and quick angular motions and adjustments, we employed ball

bearings and studs. To prevent the studs from coming out of the ball bearings and causing the model to break down while it is operating, circlips are positioned on the inner ends of the studs. Because of the way the model is constructed, the front wheel may rotate to change the direction of motion.

5.2 Working Mechanism

A 12V output power supply unit powers the model. The mild steel disc that is installed on the motor shaft begins to revolve as soon as the motor does, and it progressively picks up speed. The gyroscopic effect is created by the disc's rotation, and when the wheels lose their equilibrium because of the active gyroscopic couple, the gyroscopic effect produces a counteracting reactive gyroscopic couple in the opposite direction, stabilizing the prototype model. This gyroscopic effect is seen on the left and right sides. Thus, the prototype is stabilized as a result of the gyroscope's rotation creating a counteracting reactive gyroscopic pair. The motor and gimble axle assembly is designed in such a way that it is too heavy. This means that the center of gravity lies above the gimble axle. So, the motor and gyroscope assembly try to attain the position such that the center of gravity of the core will move downwards. But at the same time the motor and gimble assembly is arranged within the frame having bearing reaction at ends. So, the only possible way for motor to attain the stability is to either lean forward or backward. So, when the motor is started the body is about to fall on either side and also the motor assembly is leaning this causes the precession of spin axis. The reactive gyroscopic couple operates on the frame as a result of this precession, in accordance with the right hand rule, neutralizing the impact of the disturbing couple and stabilizing the vehicle. The gyroscope experiences pure rolling motion about the spin axis once the motor and frame have completed a few rotations and oscillations.

6. COMPONENTS & SPECIFICATIONS

1. Gyroscope Disc

Specifications:

1. Diameter of the Disc = 64cms
2. Weight of the Disc = 16kgs
3. Type of material = MS (mild steel)

2. DC motor

Specifications:

1. Speed of the motor = 2800 RPM
2. Voltage = 24V
3. Power = 500 watts

3. Battery

Specifications:(60V 28.6AH)-NMC

4. Bearings and Fasteners

7. FABRICATION IMAGE

8. CALCULATIONS

8.1 Block Diagram

Sketch showing the parameters when the vehicle is leaning

8.2 Mass & Weight Calculations

- Weight of the Chassis =30kgs
 - Weight of the Gyroscope disc =16kgs
 - Weight of the Motor =5kgs
 - Weight of the Batteries =10kgs
 - Weight of the Frames =20kgs
 - Weight of the Fittings & Fasteners =6kgs
 - Weight of the Human =70kgs
- Total Weight of the Vehicle = 82kgs

8.3 Design Calculations

Formulas:

1. Moment of Inertia, $I = mr^2/2$

- m = mass of the disc
- r = radius of the disc

$$I = \frac{16 \times 0.32 \times 0.32}{2}$$

$$I = 0.819 \text{ kg-m}^2$$

2. Angular momentum, $I \omega = m \times r^2 \times \pi \times N / 60$

- m = mass of the disc
- r = radius of the disc
- N = speed of the disc

$$= \frac{16 \times 0.32 \times 0.32 \times 3.14 \times 2800}{60}$$

$$I \omega = 240.08 \text{ kg-m}^2/\text{s}$$

3. Precision speed of disc, $\omega_p = \frac{M \times g \times h \times \sin(\Theta)}{I \omega}$

- Θ = tilt angle
- $I \omega$ = angular momentum
- h = height of vehicle from the ground

$$= \frac{16 \times 9.81 \times 1.3 \times \sin(15)}{240.08}$$

$$\omega_p = 0.219 \text{ m/s}^2$$

4. Gyroscope Torque, $T = I \omega \times \omega_p$

- $I \omega$ = angular momentum
- ω_p = precision speed of the disc

$$= 240.08 \times 0.219$$

$$T = 52.57 \text{ kg-m}^2/\text{s}$$

9. FUTURE SCOPE

User Interface Integration: Gyroscope systems could be integrated with user interfaces, such as smartphone apps or dashboard displays, providing real-time feedback on the vehicle's balance status, calibration options, and diagnostic information.

Regulatory Considerations: As with any emerging technology in the automotive industry, regulatory frameworks will need to adapt to accommodate self-balancing electric vehicles equipped with gyroscopes. This includes safety standards, licensing requirements, and guidelines for autonomous features.

Market Adoption: The acceptance and adoption of self-balancing electric two-wheelers will depend not only on technological advancements but also on factors like cost, reliability, and user acceptance. Marketing strategies and public awareness campaigns will play a crucial role in popularizing these vehicles.

Autonomous Features: Gyroscopes can serve as a fundamental component for autonomous or semi-autonomous riding features. They can aid in maintaining stability and can be integrated with other sensors for navigation, obstacle detection, and collision avoidance.

Adaptive Riding Experience: Advanced gyroscopes coupled with AI algorithms could enable personalized riding experiences, adjusting the vehicle's balance and handling characteristics based on the rider's preferences, road conditions, and other factors.

Energy Efficiency: Optimizing gyroscope systems to be energy-efficient can help mitigate the additional power consumption they might introduce. This could involve improvements in sensor technology, as well as integrating them with the vehicle's power management systems.

Compact and Lightweight Designs: Future gyroscopes could be designed to be smaller, lighter, and more affordable without sacrificing performance. This would facilitate easier integration into electric two-wheelers without significantly impacting their overall weight or cost.

10. CONCLUSION

The prototype indicated above was created and built to validate the idea that gyroscopes, which are often employed in ships and airplanes primarily for stabilization reasons, may also be utilized efficiently for a two-wheeled vehicle's self-stabilization. The design and construction of a two-wheeled self-balancing vehicle with a straightforward design is shown in this research project. For two-wheeled vehicles, such a system can be quite beneficial in lowering accidents or unintentional falls and raising rider safety.

11. REFERENCE

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